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The Slope Gradient And Surface Runoff Dynamics Of Selected River Floodplains In Yenagoa And Its Environs, Bayelsa State

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ABSTRACT

The study carried out assessment of the slope gradient of the floodplains of Epie, Kolo and Ekole Rivers in order to identify points which generate higher surface runoff. The three rivers making up the study area was subdivided into three equal sections \corresponding to the upper, middle and lower segments of the rivers. The study covered area within 0 and 500 meters, moving offshore of the bank of each segment of the rivers. Data on the absolute relief (AR) of the area was extracted from a digital elevation model (DEM) that was extracted from the Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) using arc-hydro GIS 10.4 where the relative relief (RR) where calculated using formulas. The data on the RR were presented graphically to show the elevation differences. Thus, from the graphs, the slope gradients were determined using appropriate formula. The results of the study have shown that slope gradient varies from segments to another which also results in variation in the surface runoff at different segments of the rivers. The study therefore, recommends the dredging and filling of low-lands found within the middle and lower segments of Kolo River as well as control of human activities within areas identified to have higher slope gradients on the floodplains of the three rivers.

Keywords: Slope Gradient, Floodplain, Relative Relief, Surface Runoff.

INTRODUCTION

The surface of the earth is a variable factor that changes from point to point. These changes produce slopes of varying orientation and gradients or magnitude. Slopes can be seen as the vertical inclination between the hill top and the valley bottom in an area. This can be explained by the horizontal line spacing of contours and can be expressed generally in degrees or percentage decline or increase (Wajid, 2021). In general, slope or gradient of a surface area can be described as change in elevation (a rise) over the corresponding change in the horizontal position (a run) and expressed in degree or as a percentage (Bolstad, 2012).

Vinogradove (2022) has pointed out that slopes are the main element of hilly or mountain relief terrains and that the physics of runoff generation for both hilly and on plains is the same but however, the processes are more rigorous in mountain terrains. Thus, the determination of slopes from contour maps can only be amenable in mountain terrains where the differences in elevation of the earth surface are visible. In floodplain where the terrain is relatively flat; measuring slopes by contours could be very

difficult. Therefore, the slope of such areas can be determined graphically from a plot of elevation-distance of the surface area and taking any angle from a straight line (www.mathcentre.ac.uk, 2009). The slope of any surface comprises two major components namely; 'gradient' and 'aspect' (Ross, 2004). Whereas, the gradient of a slope refers to the maximum rate of change in the elevation of a plane; the 'slope aspect' is used to describe the direction of the plane with reference to some arbitrary zero (usually with respect to any of the cardinal points). Again, slopes can be described as positive; where the inclined plane increases upwards from left to right (www.mathcentre.ac.uk, 2009). On the other hand, for a negative slope, the line of inclination is found to decrease downwards from left to right while, for a zero slope gradient, the elevation remains the constant over a distance along the horizontal line (www.mathcentre.ac.uk, 2009). See figures 1a, b, c.

Figure 1. Slope Direction on an Inclined Plane (Coppied from www.mathcentre.ac.uk., 2009)

Nelson (2015) has noted that slope can be expressed as a gradient, where it is used to describe the difference in the vertical and horizontal excecration of a surface which in algebraic terms, can be defined as the ratio of the rise (elevation) and the run (distance). Hence, the slope gradient can be expressed in percentage rise or drop over a distance. For instance, as explained by (Nelson, 2015), if a land surface drops 10 meters over a distance of 100 meters; the area is said to produce a gradient of 0.1 (that is; 10/100)

The slope of a terrain controls many geological and hydrological processes including the runoff and accumulation of water (Nelson, 2015). Hence, figure 1; water falling on the surface at points A and B is expected to run downhill but at point C, surface runoff may not be visible and can result into accumulation of water. This brings us to the concept of *surface runoff* which has been defined as the portion of precipitation (in form of rainfall) that falls on the surface earth and makes its way towards rivers, or other depression storage or flat areas (Garg, 2012).

Balasubramanian (2017) has pointed out that, surface runoff in terms of overland flow begins when the rate of rainfall is greater than the rate of infiltration of the soil and is further exacerbated by the amount or degree of slope. Hence, surface runoff depends on the type or orientation of the slope and the magnitude of the inclination of the surface. Therefore, the precipitation that comes inform of rainfall can be translated to surface runoff as a result of the excess water that could not infiltrate through the soil pores to occupy a space in the water table due to various factors. Garg (2012) has broadly categorized these factors into two types namely; the characteristics of the precipitation (e.g. duration and intensity) and the drainage basin characteristics (e.g basin size, shape and elevation).

The floodplain has been described as a relatively flat terrain. In terms of the morphology, Okolie (2016) has described a floodplain as an area of land in a watershed that is generally flat; prone to flooding and; next to a river stretching from banks to the outer edges of the valley. Similarly, Bridge (2003) has described the dimension of a floodplain to be a relatively flat land area which progressively decreases in elevation towards a river channel but however, at areas very close to the river; there exists a strip of land referred to as a levee which is slightly higher in elevation. Again, Umeuduji (2017) has described a floodplain as a geomorphic feature with a fairly level land usually aligned on either sides of a river.

It was noted that slopes are more visible in hilly and mountainous areas than plain terrains (Vinogradove, 2022). But the floodplain environment may not be so flat and leveled at all points. This implies that some points within the floodplain are expected to be lower or higher in elevation than other points. This little difference in the elevation is the result of the formation of slopes of varying degrees that controls the movement of water (surface runoff rate) at different points within the floodplain terrain.

Most studies have tried to investigate runoff potential of a watershed through morphometric analysis of watersheds (e.g. Kulkarni, 2013; Igbai & Saijad, 2014). Watershed morphometry has been defined as the measurement and mathematical analysis of the configuration of the earth's surface, shape and dimension of its landform (Kulkarni, 2013; Igbai & Saijad, 2014). Some other studies have tried to investigate the influence of some morphometric parameters to the surface runoff potential of watersheds using relief morphometric parameters such as the relief ratio Rh , and ruggedness number Rn , where; higher values depicts higher chances of flooding due to high surface runoff (Luo & Harlin, 2003; Singh et al., 2008; Bhatt & Ahmed, 2013; Mushen and Syed 2017; Supriya et al., 2019).

This present study falls within the Yenagoa Metropolis which is flood prone hence; water falling on the surface in form of precipitation is difficult to runoff. Again, does it also mean that slopes are relatively insignificant? Although, studies have been carried out on the elevation differences of the land surface within the study area indicating that the area prone to flooding (e.g Wizer & Agbabou, 2014; Moses *et al.*, 2020); It further showed that the area is not so flat but there are some variation in the elevation of the surface from point to point.

These differences may result to the formation of slopes of varying sizes and magnitude. Thus, in the events of the study of how prone the area is to flooding, much attention has not been giving to how the difference in the elevation of the surface of the floodplains of these rivers can form slopes of varying magnitude (slope gradients) that may control the movement of water within the area. The present study focuses on the assessing the slope gradient (as a result of the differences in surface elevation) of the floodplains of Epie, Kolo and Ekole Rivers with the aim of determining the dynamics of surface runoff at various segments of each of the river floodplain.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework.

i.) Theories on Motion of Bodies on an Inclined Surface

The fundamental principle of the Aristotle's theory on Motion was that: "*for an object to be in motion, another object (he called the mover) must induce it*" (Oliveira, 2022). Thus he (Aristotle) made his assertion that; "*The times it takes for a body to travel a distance is inversely proportional to the motive power of the mover.*" This statement can be interpreted to mean that; for a body (called the 'moved') to be set in motion, there must be a force from an external body called the 'mover' and is bounded by four kinds of forces namely, pulling, pushing, carrying and twirling. Hence, proponents of the theory further claimed that, for a body (the moved) to be set in motion, it must make a direct contact with the external force (the mover) compelling it to move (Oliveira, 2022).

Therefore, on the watershed point of view, it has been observed that, water falling on the earth surface (inform of precipitation) make direct contact with the surface earth and depending on the shape of the surface in terms of the slope; water can either flow downhill (in form of surface runoff) or accumulate on the earth surface to form a pool of water (as described in Fig.1). Hence, the rate of flow of water or surface runoff (being the moved) on the earth surface can be induced by the slope gradient (magnitude of the slope) which is the inclination surface that forms the slope in terms of the gradient (being the mover). The conceptual framework is on Slope Gradient-Surface Runoff Relationship as shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2. Conceptual Framework on Slope Gradient-Surface Runoff Relationship (Authors' concept).

It has been noted that slopes are formed as a result of the variation in the elevation on the earth surface. Hence, the rate of surface runoff depends on the degree of slope (gradient) formed by the inclination line between the highest and lowest points in terms of elevation. Therefore, buttressing the facts on the above framework, most studies have pointed to the fact that areas characterized by high slope gradient results to increased surface runoff (Masoudian and Theobald, 2011; Bhunia et' al., 2012; Morges and Bhole 2015; Nguyen, et'al 2017; Mukhtar, *et al.*, 2018; MST, 2019). Again, Altin (2017) has noted that areas with low relief reduce the theoretical travel time of water thereby resulting to accumulation of water while points with high degree of slope easily results to shorter travel duration by water.

METHODS

Study Area

The study area covers Yenagoa and its environs located between latitudes 004.3500 °N and 005.00 °N and between Longitudes 006.250 °E and 006.500 °E. The area covers communities located along the Epie, Kolo and Ekole River floodplains which comprise communities within the Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state. The three rivers dissects the Yenagoa town into three sections namely; the Epie Creek (which is placed central), the Kolo Creek (which is located east), and the Ekole Creek (which is located west) of Yenagoa respectively.

These three rivers are selected based on the fact that almost all the communities in the study area are located on the floodplains of these rivers (See Figure 3). Most areas on these floodplains were once agricultural lands for the production of mainly cassava, water-yam, cocoyam, and variety of vegetables. Presently, the area is fast undergoing some form of transformation mainly, urbanization since 1996 when Yenagoa town was made a state capital.

Fig. 3. Map of the Yenagoa metropolis Showing Epie, Kolo and Ekole Creeks in Yenagoa Metropolis.

Data Collection

The study area as shown in figure 3 covered a total area of 30.6km² (=0.5km by 30.6km by 2) comprising the left and right flanks of Epie sub-watershed; 29.16 km² (=0.5km by 29.16 by 2) comprising the Kolo left and right flanks; and 19.80km² (=0.5km by 19.80km by 2) comprising the Ekole left and right flanks respectively. Thus, for ease of data collection; each of the river floodplain was subdivided into three sections (10.20 km² for Epie; 9.72km² for Kolo & 6.60km² for Ekole), which corresponds to the upper, middle and lower segments of the rivers and their floodplains (see Appendix I, II & III).

Again, the study also covered an area between 0.00meters to 500meters (0.5km) inland for the left and right banks of each river floodplain. This is because, at most points along these rivers, development by occupants of the area have encroached the floodplains into the rivers which is even visible during below bank-full stage. Hence, at each of the segments, the floodplains were subdivided into five (5) sampling points of 100meters moving inland from the left and right flanks or banks of the rivers.

Data on the relief morphometric parameters was determined from a digital elevation model (DEM) that was extracted from the Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) using arc-hydro GIS 10.4 which was used to obtain the absolute relief (AR) for each sampling points. Hence, the relative relief (RR) of the floodplains was obtained for the various sampling points using mathematical formula adopted from the literature (e.g. Karim 2020) as shown in equation 1.

$$RR = H - h \dots\dots\dots 1$$

(Where, RR is the basin relief; H is the maximum elevation relative to the other points, while h , is the minimum elevation relative to the other points).

Thus, the RR was calculated by subtracting the higher elevation H from the lower elevation as shown in equation 1 for each of the segments along the rivers (upper, middle & lower).

Thus, the differences in the elevation of the surface in terms of the relative relief (RR) were obtained for the five (5) sample points of one hundred meters (100m) each beginning from the banks or natural levee to a distance of 500m (0.5km) away from the shores of each of the rivers. Secondly, the values of the RR calculated were used to determine the slope for each segment of the rivers (upper, middle and lower) by graphical method as suggested in www.mathcentre.ac.uk. (2009) using the formula as presented in equation 2 (a & b);

$$\text{Slope (\%)} = (dy / dx) \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 2. a$$

$$\text{Slope Gradient (degree)} = \tan^{-1}(dy/dx) \dots\dots\dots 2. b$$

(Where; dy = change in vertical elevation, and dx = change in horizontal elevation).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The values of the absolute relief (AR) and relative relief (RR) of the left and right flanks of Epie, Kolo and Ekole River floodplains were obtained as presented in Appendices IV to IX for the respective segments (upper, middle and lower). Hence, the values of the RR for the various segments were used to plot a graph of the change in the elevation with distance moving offshore from the banks of the rivers (See fig. 4, 5 & 6). Hence, the slope gradients for each of the segments of the three rivers were determined using formula as presented in equation 2b (see table 1).

The results of the analysis as presented in table 1 show that, for both flanks of the three river floodplains; slope gradient of the area ranges between 10° and 67° for the Epie River; 0° and 54° for the Kolo River; and between 33° and 104° for the Ekole River respectively. Thus, on the Epie River Floodplain, results show that, slope gradient ranges between 10° and 67° . Hence, the slope gradient was found to decrease moving downstream for the left flank but a slight increase was found on the right flank. Again, results further shows that, the upper-left segment (61°) and middle-right segment (67°) of the floodplain of Epie River are points characterized by relatively higher slope gradient than the lower-left (15°) and upper-right (10°) being the lowest. See Appendix 1 for the corresponding communities.

Epie

Fig4. Slope Gradient of the Segments of Epie River Floodplain (left and right) Kolo

Fig 5. Slope Gradient of the Segments of Kolo River Floodplain (left and right).

Ekole

Fig. 6. Slope Gradient of the Segments of Ekole River Floodplain (left and right)

Table 1. Slope Gradient (in degree) of Epie, Kolo and Ekolo Floodplains

River Channel	Floodplain Segment	Left Flank Gradient(\tan^{-1})	Right Flank Gradient(\tan^{-1})
Epie	Upper	61°	10°
	Middle	20°	67°
	Lower	15°	46°
Kolo	Upper	54°	18°
	Middle	10°	0°
	Lower	38°	0°
Ekole	Upper	61°	98°
	Middle	104°	88°
	Lower	101°	33°

Source: Authors' Fieldwork (2023).

Along the Kolo River floodplain, results also showed that the slope gradient ranges between 0° and 54° and were found to slightly decrease downstream on the left flank but there is a sharp decrease in the slope gradient on the right flank. Also, the slope gradient of the upper-left segment (54°) and the upper-right segment (18°) are found to be relatively higher than the adjoining segments. But the middle-right

and lower-right segments are found to have a zero slope gradient. See Appendix II for the corresponding communities.

Again, along Ekole River floodplain, results have shown that slope gradient ranges between 33° and 104° with an increase in the slope gradient moving downstream on the left flank; but a decrease in the slope gradient occurs on the right flank of the floodplain. Again, results has further shown that, the middle-left (104°) and the lower-left (101°) segments as well as the upper-right (98°) and middle-right (88°) segments are found to have higher slope gradient than upper-left (61°) and the lower-right (33°) segments of the floodplain. See Appendix III for the corresponding communities.

With regards to the results, the study found that there that the floodplains of Epie, Kolo and Ekole Rivers are not that flat but rather, there are differences in the elevation at different points which forms slopes of varying degrees that can initiates surface runoff in the event of any rainfall. Also, the results have shown that the slope gradient of the left flank of Epie River as well as the left and right flanks of Kolo River were found to decrease in the downstream direction from upper to the lower segments. This in line with the work of Nguyen, et'al (2017) which asserts that, slope gradients along rivers are expected to decrease moving downstream. But this was not the case with the right flank of Epie River as well as the left and right flanks of Ekole River floodplains which showed an increase in the slope gradient moving downstream.

Again studies have shown that, areas on the floodplains with higher slope gradient are expected to generate higher surface runoff while the reverse would lead to accumulation of water in the event of any rainfall(e.g Masoudian and Theobald, 2011; Bhunia et' al., 2012; Morges and Bhole 2015; Danacova et' al., 2017; Vanlaltanpuia et' al., 2018; Wajid, 2021). Hence, this study has also found out that slope gradient of the upper-left and middle-right segments of Epie River; upper-left and upper-right segments of Kolo River; as well as the middle-left and upper-right segments of Ekole River are relatively higher than their adjoining segment; therefore, surface runoff is expected to be higher within these segments. On the other hand, areas within the middle and lower-right segment of Kolo River floodplain with slope gradient of 0° is expected to be water logged area. Again, the slope gradient within the middle-left (20°) as well as the lower-left segment (15°) of Epie River and within the middle-left (10°) which are found to be relatively lower can be said to generate lower surface runoff due to lesser power to push water away from the area. This is in line with the conceptual and theoretical framework of this study as explained in Oliveira, (2022).

CONCLUSION

The study of slope gradient of the floodplains of Epie, Kolo and Ekole has shown areas with varying surface runoff potential at different segments along the rivers. This is due to the differences in the degree of slope produced by the undulating pattern of the earth surface. The results have shown that, the surface of the floodplain of Epie, Kolo and Ekole Rivers are not evenly distributed but characterized by varying elevations. It is the differences in the elevation at the various segments that produces slopes of varying magnitude that influences surface runoff in terms of overland flow.

In general, the study has found out that the slope gradient of the various segments were relatively higher at the Ekole River floodplain followed by those of Epie River floodplain with those of the Kolo River floodplain being the least. This would also imply that, the floodplain of the Ekole River is likely to generate more runoff than those of Epie and Kolo Rivers. The study has also found the middle and lower segments (right) of Kolo River floodplain to be relatively flat which means that, the area is water logged and could be susceptible to flooding.

The study therefore recommends relocation of residents within the middle and lower segments (left) of the Kolo River floodplain to higher lands during the wet season. Also, dredging of the Kolo River to fill these depressions can go a long way to support the development of the area. Again, floodplain mapping and land use activities should be controlled and monitored in areas with relatively high slope gradients. This will also help to check development activities that would avert environmental disaster in terms of effects arising from erosion of the land surface.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Sampling Points along the Epie Creek (with Sample length of 30.6km)

Section/Sampling Points	Cumm Length (Km)	Location/Community	Geo-reference	Points
Upper Segment				
I	3.40	Igbogene	05-04 32 °N, 06.4076 °E	
II	6.80	Akenfa	04.9390 °N, 06.3757 °E	
III	10.20	Agudama	04.9858 °N, 06.3750 °E	
Middle Segment				
I	13.60	Edepie	04.9793 °N, 06.3672 °E	
II	17.00	Biogbolo	04.6921 °N, 06.3655°E	
III	20.40	Kpansia	04.9495 °N, 06.3326 °E	
Lower Segment				
I	23.80	Amarata	04.9328 °N, 06.2889 °E	
II	27.20	Onopa	04.9362 °N, 06.2640 °E	
III	30.60	Yenagoa Town	04.9248 °N, 06.2584 °E	

Source: Author's Field Measurement (2023).

Appendix II: Sampling Points along the Kolo Creek (withinth length of 29.16km)

Section/Sampling Points	Cumm Length (Km)	Location/Community	Geo-reference	Points
Upper Segment				
I	3.24	Etegwe II	04.9341 °N, 06.4184 °E	
II	6.48	Ibelebiri	04.9572 °N, 06.4363 °E	
III	9.72	Oruma	04.9172 °N, 06.4170 °E	
Middle Segment				
I	12.96	Otusega	04.9150 °N, 06.4020 °E	
II	16.20	Shell Camp	04.8798 °N, 06.3756 °E	
III	19.44	Imiringi	04.8522 °N, 06.3704°E	
Lower Segment				
I	22.68	Emeyal II	04.8386 °N, 06.3524 °E	
II	25.29	Emeyal	104.8240 °N, 06.3623 °E	
III	29.16	Kolo Town	04.8030 °N, 06.3765 °E	

Source: Author's Field Measurement (2023)

Appendix III: Sampling Points along the Ekole Creek within the length of 19.80km

Section/Sampling Cumm	Location/	Geo-reference
Points	Length (Km)	Community
Upper Segment		
I	2.20	Yenaka
II	4.40	Famgbe
III	6.80	Ogu
Middle Segment		
I	9.00	Oxbow-Lake
II	11.20	Dawoo Jetty
III	13.20	Agbura
Lower Segment		
I	15.40	Otuokpoti
II	17.60	Otuogori
III	19.80	Onuebum

Source: Author's Field Measurement (2023)

Appendix IV. Absolute Relief (AR) of Epic Creek Left and Right Floodplains

Stream segment	LEFT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel					Epic Creek (AR)	RIGHT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel				
	500	400	300	200	100		100	200	300	400	500
Upper	16	12	10	12	10	10	12	13	13	11	12
Middle	16	16	14	11	8	7	12	14	16	18	19
Lower	10	10	10	11	10	7	9	12	12	14	14
Mean	14.00	12.67	11.33	11.33	9.33	8.00	11.00	13.00	11.67	14.33	15.00

Source: Authors' fieldwork (2023).

Appendix V. Absolute Relief (AR) of Kolo Creek Left and Right Floodplains

Stream segment	LEFT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel					Kolo Creek	RIGHT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel				
	500	400	300	200	100		100	200	300	400	500
Upper	16	15	16	14	11	9	10	11	15	15	17
Middle	16	15	13	11	12	13	11	12	16	17	19
Lower	19	21	19	16	12	9	11	13	14	15	17
Mean	17.00	17.00	16.00	13.67	11.67	10.33	10.67	12.00	15.00	15.87	17.67

Source: Authors' fieldwork (2023).

Appendix VI. Absolute Relief (AR) of Ekole Creek Left and Right Floodplains

Stream segment	LEFT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel					Ekole Creek	RIGHT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel				
	500	400	300	200	100		100	200	300	400	500
Upper	16	12	8	6	5	3	4	4	5	8	13
Middle	16	18	17	15	15	3	9	12	15	16	15
Lower	17	16	17	15	10	3	15	15	14	14	14
Mean	16.33	15.33	14.00	12.00	10.00	3.00	9.33	10.33	11.33	12.67	14.00

Source: Authors' fieldwork (2023).

Appendix VII. The Relative Relief (RR) of Epie Creek Floodplains (Left/Right)

Stream segment	LEFT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel					Epie Creek (AR)	RIGHT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel				
	500	400	300	200	100		100	200	300	400	500
Upper	4	1	2	2	0	10	2	1	0	2	1
Middle	0	2	3	3	1	7	5	2	2	2	1
Lower	0	0	1	1	3	7	2	3	0	2	0
Mean	1.33	1.00	2.00	2.00	1.33		3.00	2.00	0.67	2.00	0.67

Source: Authors' fieldwork (2023).

Appendix VIII. Relative Relief (RR) of Kolo Creek Floodplains

Stream segment	LEFT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel					Kolo Creek (AR)	RIGHT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel				
	500	400	300	200	100		100	200	300	400	500
Upper	1	1	2	3	3	9	1	1	4	0	2
Middle	1	2	2	1	1	13	2	1	4	1	2
Lower	2	2	3	4	3	9	2	1	1	1	2
Mean	1.33	1.67	2.33	2.67	2.33		1.67	1.00	3.00	0.67	2.00

Source: Authors' fieldwork (2023).

Appendix IX. Relative Relief (RR) of Ekole Creek Floodplains

Stream segment	LEFT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel					Ekole Creek	RIGHT PLAIN Meters Away From the Channel					
	500	400	300	200	100		100	200	300	400	500	
Upper	4	4	2	1	2	3	1	0	1	1	8	5
Middle	2	1	2	0	12	3	6	3	3	1	1	1
Lower	1	1	2	5	7	3	2	0	1	0	0	0
Mean	2.33	2.00	2.00	2.00	7.67	3	3	1	1.67	3	2	

Source: Authors' fieldwork (2023).